

CHEMISTRY OF BERYLLIUM. PART III. COMPOUNDS OF BERYLLIUM
CHLORIDE WITH AMINOPHENOLS, AMINO BENZOIC ACIDS,
p-NITROANILINE AND 2:4-DINITROPHENYLHYDRAZINE

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Complex compounds of aminophenols, aminobenzoic acids, *p*-nitroaniline and 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazine with beryllium chloride have been prepared and their constitution discussed. Salts of the complexes of aminophenols and aminobenzoic acids have been prepared.

A survey of literature shows that no work has been done on the complex formation of beryllium chloride with aminophenols, aminobenzoic acids, *p*-nitroaniline and 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazine. The present work was therefore undertaken with a view to studying the formation of complex compounds of beryllium chloride with these substances. Beryllium salts of the amino acids and aminophenols were also prepared.

EXPERIMENTAL

Anhydrous beryllium chloride was prepared by the method of Pollok (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1904, 85, 603). Excess of chlorine was removed by passing dry carbon dioxide. It was extracted with ether, dehydrated over sodium.

Two types of complexes, (A) addition and (B) addition-cum-substitution, have been prepared.

(A) *Addition Complexes*

On mixing separately ethereal solution of beryllium chloride with aminophenols, aminobenzoic acids and *p*-nitroaniline, complex compounds separated out immediately. The precipitate was allowed to settle and the supernatant liquid decanted through a dry filter paper. The precipitate was repeatedly washed with dry ether till the filtrate did not respond to tests of the reactants. The precipitate was then transferred to the filter paper, filter-pressed and finally dried in vacuum.

The complex compound with *m*-aminobenzoic acid was also prepared by suspending the acid in minimum quantity of absolute alcohol and then adding an ethereal solution of BeCl₂. The complex formed dissolved, leaving behind the excess acid; the mixture was allowed to stand for an hour with frequent shaking and filtered. The filtrate on evaporation gave the pure compound.

In the case of nitroaniline, only half of the complex compound separated out. On evaporating the filtrate, a yellow compound was obtained which on further purification by repeated washings with dry benzene gave a similar compound.

Compounds with 2:4-Dinitrophenylhydrazine.—2:4-Dinitrophenylhydrazine was taken in a glass-stoppered conical flask, cooled in ice and an excess of ethereal solution of BeCl_2 added (1:1 ratio). The mixture was allowed to stand in ice for an hour with frequent shaking after which it was brought to the room temperature and shaken well for about 2 hours. Nearly 10 c.c. of BeCl_2 solution (1.6 g./100 c.c. ether) was again added and the mixture shaken well for some time and then left overnight. The compound obtained was purified by repeated washing with dry ether. It was filter-pressed and dried in vacuum.

In a second experiment, dinitrophenylhydrazine was mixed with an ethereal solution of BeCl_2 in the ratio of 1:2. Ether was distilled off and the reaction mixture was heated on a water-bath for an hour to complete the reaction. It was cooled and the reaction product was repeatedly washed with dry ether and dried in vacuum.

In another experiment, the temperature was slowly raised to study the compound formed at the melting point of dinitrophenylhydrazine, but there was a violent reaction between 130° and 140° and the mixture was charred. A similar violent reaction took place when dry BeCl_2 and dinitrophenylhydrazine were heated together.

(B) Addition-cum-Substitution Complexes

Preparation of Salts of the Aminophenol and Aminobenzoic Acid Complexes.—Salts of aminophenol or amino-acid complexes were prepared by adding an ethereal solution of BeCl_2 (in slight excess of that theoretically required) to a weighed quantity of the complex. The mixture was slowly heated in an oil-bath to remove ether and the temperature was raised and maintained at $10\text{--}15^\circ$ above the m.p. of the respective phenol or acid. When the evolution of HCl had ceased, the flask was cooled and the mixture was washed repeatedly with dry ether till free of BeCl_2 . The compound obtained was filter-pressed and finally dried in vacuum. All the above reactions were carried out in the absence of moisture.

A weighed quantity of the substance was treated with dilute NaOH solution, boiled, and then neutralised with dilute HCl till slightly acidic. Beryllium was precipitated as $\text{Be}(\text{OH})_2$ and washed free of electrolyte with 2% ammonium acetate solution. $\text{Be}(\text{OH})_2$ was dissolved in dilute HCl , reprecipitated as hydroxide, washed free of electrolyte as before, dried, ignited and weighed as BeO .

Chlorine was determined by Piria and Schiff's method and nitrogen by Kjeldahl's method (except in the case of compounds containing $-\text{NO}_2$ groups).

General Properties.—All the compounds prepared are coloured, insoluble in benzene, carbon tetrachloride, ether (except the compound obtained with nitroaniline which is partially soluble), petroleum ether but soluble in alcohol. The compound obtained with *m*-aminobenzoic acid is soluble in water. Compounds obtained with 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazine change colour from chocolate-brown to orange-red when exposed to atmosphere.

TABLE I

Compounds of BeCl₂ with aminophenols, aminobenzoic acids, nitroaniline and 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazine.

Organic compounds used.	% Beryllium.		% Chlorine.		% Nitrogen.		Colour.	Compound.
	Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.		
1. <i>o</i> -Aminophenol	3.04	3.02	23.91	23.82	9.20	9.34	Dark brown	BeCl ₂ .2C ₆ H ₄ OHNH ₂
2. <i>m</i> -Aminophenol	3.03	3.02	23.88	23.82	9.22	9.34	Ash	BeCl ₂ .2C ₆ H ₄ OHNH ₂
3. <i>o</i> -Aminobenzoic acid	2.52	2.54	20.05	20.06	7.84	7.91	Light pink	BeCl ₂ .2C ₆ H ₄ COOH.NH ₂
4. <i>m</i> -Aminobenzoic acid	2.53	2.54	20.05	20.06	7.87	7.91	Brown	BeCl ₂ .2C ₆ H ₄ .NH ₂ COOH
5. <i>p</i> -Nitroaniline	2.52	2.53	19.99	19.94	...	...	Yellow	BeCl ₂ .2C ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ .NH ₂
6. 2:4-Dinitrophenylhydrazine	1.92	1.89	14.95	14.91	...	...	Chocolate	BeCl ₂ .2C ₆ H ₃ (NO ₂) ₂ NH.NH ₂
7. "	3.25	3.23	25.57	25.57	...	...	"	BeCl ₂ .C ₆ H ₃ (NO ₂) ₂ NH.NH ₂

TABLE II

Salts of the aminophenol and aminobenzoic acid complexes.

Complex compound.	% Beryllium.		% Chlorine.		% Nitrogen.		Colour.	Compound.
	Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.		
1. <i>o</i> -Aminophenol	5.97	5.90	23.19	23.28	9.06	9.18	Black	Be ₂ Cl ₃ .2C ₆ H ₄ O.NH ₂
2. <i>m</i> -Aminophenol	5.94	5.90	23.23	23.28	9.10	9.18	Dark ash	Be ₂ Cl ₃ .2C ₆ H ₄ O.NH ₂
3. <i>o</i> -Aminobenzoic acid	5.03	4.99	19.52	19.66	7.56	7.76	Light ash	Be ₂ Cl ₃ .2C ₆ H ₄ COO.NH ₂
4. <i>m</i> -Aminobenzoic acid	5.03	4.99	19.50	19.66	7.58	7.76	Light brown	Be ₂ Cl ₃ .2C ₆ H ₄ COO.NH ₂

D I S C U S S I O N

From the results it is evident that two molecules each of aminophenols, aminobenzoic acids, *p*-nitroaniline and 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazine combine with one molecule of beryllium chloride in the cold to yield the complex compounds which are similar to those obtained with aromatic amines (Prasad and Srivastava, this *Journal*, 1957, 34, 317). These can be represented as:

in the case of amidiphenol and

